

Chemistry of *Datura* Withanolides, a Brief Review[†]

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Manuscript received 7 August 1998

Datura is one of the few selected genera of the family Solanaceae that are known to elaborate withanolides — a group of steroidal lactones built on intact or rearranged ergostane framework¹. A typical withanolide may be represented by the expression 1, though a variety of oxygen substituents practically at all possible sites of the molecule are discernible in this group of compounds. Every withanolide-bearing genus has been known to yield withanolides with a characteristic substitution pattern or structural feature and the novel feature that was witnessed in withanolides of *Datura* genus is an oxygen substituent at C-21, a position where oxygen substituents were not detected earlier. Since the isolation of daturalactone-1, (2) from *Datura quercifolia* by Dhar and Raina² in 1973, forty additional withanolides have been isolated from different *Datura* species during the last twentyfive years and only three of them were previously reported from plants belonging to other genera¹, viz., *Nicandra physaloides*, *Lycium chinense* and *Withania coagulans*. The sources from which *Datura* withanolides have been isolated are reported alongwith the compounds in the structure-diagrams. Like other withanolide-bearing plants of the family Solanaceae, members of *Datura* genus have been known to show wide polymorphism³ and a great variability in both the chemical constitution and the proportion of individual withanolides in a particular species has been observed⁴. This will be evident from an inspection of withanolides isolated from *D. metel* by three different groups of workers in different parts of the world — Nohara group in Japan⁵⁻⁷, Siddiqui and his collaborators in Pakistan⁸⁻¹¹ and the author's group in India¹²⁻¹⁸.

As in the case of other groups of natural products, so also in withanolides there has been a change in the methods

of structure elucidation. Analysis of sophisticated spectral data has largely replaced classical chemical methods but it has often been necessary and also possible to provide appropriate chemical evidence in support of the structures deduced exclusively on the basis of spectral analysis. Spectral data useful for recognition of withanolide skeleton and elucidation of structure have been discussed in fair details in our earlier review article¹. A typical withanolide shows in its mass spectrum a base peak at m/z 125 (ion *a*), formed by the cleavage of C-20/C-22 bond and the diagnostic double triplet in the range δ 4.0–4.90 in its ¹H nmr spectrum. This double triplet, often regarded as withanolide 'fingerprint', is due to H-22 of withanolide and obviously, substitution at C-20 and/or C-23 simplifies the splitting pattern. ¹H nmr spectrum of a typical withanolide also shows signals for five methyl groups — two for angular C-methyls, one for a secondary C-methyl and the remaining two for vinylic methyl groups. Any observed change in the number or nature of these methyl groups suggests the modification of typical withanolide structure. The sign of Cotton effect in CD spectra provides information necessary for settling the configuration of withanolides at appropriate centres, particularly about the mode of fusion of A/B rings and the configuration at C-22. Steroids with 2-en-1-one chromophore exhibit a Cotton effect around 340 nm; the sign is positive for *cis*-fused A/B rings and negative for its *trans*-fused counterparts. Withanolides with an α,β -unsaturated- δ -lactone side-chain exhibit a positive Cotton effect around 240 nm indicating 22*R* configuration. Several withanolides including a few from *Datura* species were initially claimed to have 22*S* configuration which were eventually proved to be erroneous.

While a careful analysis of ¹H and ¹³C nmr and mass spectra of withanolides generally leads to their correct structure elucidation, an undue emphasis on only one kind of spectral data ignoring other possibilities and overlooking the information secured from other kinds of spectra may lead to advancement of a wrong structure and this is exactly what happened in the structure elucidation of daturalactones-1 and -2. Daturalactone-2, C₂₈H₃₆O₇ (M⁺, m/z 484), showed a base peak at m/z 125 in its mass spectrum and obviously it was considered¹⁹ to have an α,β -unsaturated- δ -lactone

[†] Dedicated to Dr. Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

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ring in the side-chain. ^1H nmr signals for the carbocyclic part of the molecule agreed fairly well with those of withanicandrin (9), a withanolide that was first isolated by Kirson *et al.*²⁰ from *Nicandra physaloides* and formulated as 6 α ,7 α -epoxy-5 α -hydroxy-1,12-dioxowitha-2,24-dienolide. The structure of daturalactone-2 constructed by joining the carbocyclic part of withanicandrin with the side-chain of a typical withanolide left an unaccounted oxygen function which was considered to be a tertiary hydroxyl in view of the fact that daturalactone-2 is not acylable. This tertiary hydroxyl group was conveniently placed at 17 α -position and the structure of daturalactone-2 was advanced as 5 α ,17 α -dihydroxy-1,12-dioxo-6 α ,7 α -epoxywitha-2,24-dienolide (42) ignoring the fact that the chemical shift of 27- and 28-methyl groups (δ 1.52 and 1.58 s) suggested their attachment to carbons bearing oxygen function rather than to sp^2 carbons and that the base peak at m/z 125 may also be due to ion *b*, as had been observed in the case of other 5-hydroxy-2-en-1-one withanolides²¹. Daturalactone-1 which yielded daturalactone-2 on Jones oxidation and showed ^1H nmr signal as a multiplet at δ 4.0 (W_H 5.7 Hz) was formulated as 43. Interestingly, the high field position of the hydrogen signals for 27- and 28-methyl groups were interpreted in terms of 22*S* configuration of daturalactones-1 and -2 by the authors.

The structures of daturalactones-1 and -2 were, however, revised²² by providing appropriate chemical and spectroscopic evidence in support of the presence of epoxy lactone rather than unsaturated lactone ring in the molecules. Zn–Cu couple reduction of daturalactone-1 gave a product (44), ^1H nmr spectrum of which showed the absence of signals for olefinic hydrogens at C-2 and C-3 and a downfield shift of the signals for 27- and 28-methyl groups to the expected positions of typical withanolides (δ 1.91 and 1.96). Obviously, Zn–Cu couple reduced the enone double bond of daturalactone-1 and transformed its epoxy lactone ring to α,β -unsaturated lactone. As expected, this reduction product showed positive Cotton effect at 254 nm indicating 22*R* configuration. Daturalactone-1 was thus formulated as 2.

HI reduction of daturalactone-1 yielded a trienone (λ_{max} 358 nm) the structure of which was settled as 45 from detailed spectral analysis. Daturalactone-2, the Jones oxidation product of 2, was found to be identical with the acetyl hypobromite oxidation product of Nic-7 (46), a compound of established structure and stereochemistry³³. This observation confirmed the α -configuration of the C-24/C-25 epoxide function of daturalactone-1 (2) and daturalactone-2 (3).

The *Datura* withanolide that eluded ready recognition from conventional spectral data is withametelin, isolated from the petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract of dried leaves

of *D. metel*, collected from Varanasi as well as from the suburbs of Calcutta¹². The same compound was also isolated by the Pakistani workers almost at the same time and this was named daturilin⁸. Though the source and molecular formula ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_4$) of the compound indicated it to be a withanolide and though its uv and ir data (λ_{max} 222 nm; ν_{max} 1718, 1655 cm^{-1}) spoke of the presence of enone and α,β -unsaturated- δ -lactone groupings, it failed to show any characteristic fragmentation pattern in its mass spectrum and the diagnostic withanolide fingerprint of typical withanolides in its ^1H nmr spectrum. The ^1H nmr spectrum, however, showed signals for an enone grouping, a trisubstituted olefin and only three methyl groups — two angular C-methyls and a methyl bound to a carbon bearing oxygen function. The absence of two methyl groups was, however, compensated by the presence of a terminal methylene and an oxymethylene group. While the terminal methylene was assigned to C-27 in order to fulfill the requirement of an α,β -unsaturated- δ -lactone grouping in the molecule and justify the appearance of its two hydrogen signals as singlets at δ 6.02 and 6.76 in its ^1H nmr spectrum, it was rather difficult to ascertain from conventional spectral data which of the two remaining methyl

groups was oxygenated. Under the circumstances, two alternative structures (35 and 35a) were advanced for withametelin keeping in view that it is not acylable under normal conditions and that valency calculation demanded it to be hexacyclic. The non-conjugated trisubstituted double bond was placed between 5 and 6 positions on biogenetic consideration but an unambiguous evidence in its support was provided by epoxidation and mercuric acetate oxidation of withametelin. Epoxidation of withametelin with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid yielded a mixture of epoxides which was separated by hplc into two isomeric compounds showing mirror image Cotton effects at 345 nm, indicating thereby the formation of both AB-*cis*- and AB-*trans*- fused compounds. The non-conjugated double bond that can generate such a mixture must be between 5 and 6 positions and obviously the products formed were 5 α ,6 α - and 5 β ,6 β -epoxides of withametelin (47 and 48). Hg(OAc)₂ oxidation of withametelin yielded an acetate derivative (49) with a conjugated dienone chromophore (λ_{max} 310 nm). It is well known³⁴ that mercuric acetate which gives allyl acetate from an olefin does not insert the acetoxy group at the allylic position but rather attacks on the double bond and makes it migrate. The formation of 49 from withametelin thus provided additional evidence in support of 2,5-dien-1-one system. The β -orientation of the acetoxy group at C-6 position of 49 was settled from the chemical shift of 19-methyl group

(δ 1.35 s)³⁵. A choice between the two alternatives 35 and 35a was made by hydrogenolysis and methanolysis experiments. An inspection of the two structures reveals that the oxide bridge is present as an allyl ether in 35 and not in 35a. It was, therefore, surmised that if 35 represents the correct structure of withametelin, it should undergo hydrogenolysis. Catalytic reduction of withametelin with Pd-C (5%) yielded a tetrahydro derivative (50) as a minor constituent and it showed, like typical withanolides, a base peak at *m/z* 125 in its mass spectrum, the diagnostic double triplet at δ 4.37 (*J* 13.5, 3.6 Hz) and signals for two vinylic methyl groups at δ 1.88 and 1.93 in its ¹H nmr spectrum and a positive Cotton effect at 250 nm signifying 22*R* configuration. Methanolysis of withametelin was effected by treatment of 35 with MeOH and HClO₄ at room temperature and the product formed by 1,4-addition of MeOH was identified as secowithametelin (16), a compound that was isolated from *D. metel* both by the Japanese workers⁶ as well as by us¹⁴. Based on these observations withametelin was proved to have a cyclic allyl ether function and its structure was conclusively settled as 35. The correctness of this structure was also verified by ¹³C shift correlation two dimensional spectrum (2D INADEQUATE), showing carbon-carbon connectivity and establishing that the oxymethylene carbon is bound to C-20 and not C-24. The configuration at C-24 shown in the structure 35 is based on the finding that a Dreiding stereomodel of withametelin demands 28-methyl group and H-22 to be on the same side of the lactone ring. The report of the isolation of daturilin from *D. metel* by Pakistani workers⁸ appeared almost simultaneously with that of withametelin¹². Daturilin was assigned the same gross structure as 35 but with a 22*S* configuration based nOe difference measurements. There are reasons to believe that daturilin is identical with withametelin. Withametelin underwent a dienone-phenol type rearrangement with Ac₂O-HClO₄ to give a ring-A aromatic withanolide (51) with concomitant opening of the bicyclic side-chain. This observation is of significance in view of the occurrence of ring A aromatic withanolides in some solanaceous plants¹.

Isowithametelin (34), a congener of withametelin, was

considered to have 3,5-dien-1-one grouping in place of a 2,5-dien-1-one system present in withametelin from comprehensive spectral analysis. A two-step transformation of withametelin (35) to isowithametelin (34) involving ketalisation and subsequent deketalisation reaction verified the correctness of the structure of isowithametelin.

Shingu and coworkers reported the isolation of polar withanolides from *Datura* species; glycowithanolides daturametelins A, B and G from *D. metel*^{5,6} and daturaturins A and B from *D. tatura*²⁵. Withanolide hydrogen sulphates, daturametelins E and F were also isolated by these workers from *D. metel*⁶. These workers considered withametelin (35) to be an artefact derived from daturametelin B (13) by S_N2' -type reaction during chromatography over silica gel. This argument is not acceptable because withametelin was isolated in a fairly good yield (0.1%) from the petroleum ether extract of the plant material, collected during the months of September and December, and daturametelin B, a glycoside, is not likely to be extracted with this solvent. The suggestion that withametelin might be a product of dry leaves and not fresh ones (personal communication) is also not valid as the Pakistani workers isolated it from the fresh leaves of *D. metel*. Further, if the presence of cyclic allyl ether system, as is present in withametelin (35), becomes a criterion of being an artefact, daturametelin F (33) isolated by the Japanese workers⁶ should also be an artefact but no such claim has been made by these workers. It may be pertinent to mention in this connection that 21,27-dihydroxywithanolides when adsorbed on silica gel and then heated at 110° for 1h or more, a substantial amount of it is converted to withametelin-type hexacyclic withanolides with bicyclic side-chain (unpublished work). It is, therefore, quite possible that daturametelin B (13) or its equivalent is the precursor of withametelin.

Daturametelin F, one of the two known withanolide sulphates, was isolated from *D. metel*⁶ as an amorphous powder. It showed a peak at m/z 533 (M-H)⁻ in its negative ionisation FAB mass spectrum. A comparison of ¹H nmr spectrum of daturametelin F with that of withametelin (35) revealed that hydrogen signals associated with BCD rings and side-chain of the two compounds were in perfect agreement. Daturametelin F, however, failed to show hydrogen signals for the enone system and instead showed a low-field 1H signal at δ 5.07 which was assigned to H-3 as it was

proved to be flanked between a ketomethylene and an allylic methylene group from ¹H-¹H cosy nmr spectrum. The presence of a sulphate group in the molecule was surmised from its ir band at 1226 cm⁻¹ and appropriate colour reaction, and verified by solvolytic desulphation with pyridine-dioxane mixture to give the corresponding alcohol (signal for H-3 shifted from δ 5.07 to 3.86). Conclusive evidence in support of the structure 33 for daturametelin F came from its conversion to withametelin (35) by treatment with pyridine and acetic anhydride.

Withafastuosin B, isolated from the leaves of *D. fastuosa* was recognised to be a close relative of withametelin F, the 5 β ,6 β -epoxide of withametelin, from spectral comparison. Unlike withametelin F, however, withafastuosin B yielded a monoacetate on acetylation with Ac₂O-pyridine at room temperature and showed no hydrogen signal for an exocyclic methylene group in its ¹H nmr spectrum but showed two sets of ABX pattern for a pair of -CH-CH₂-O- groupings. While one set of signals which remained unchanged on acetylation was due to methine and methylene hydrogens of C-20 and C-21 respectively, the other showing a downfield shift in its monoacetate (δ 2.58, 1H, dd, J 5.2, 3.6 Hz; 4.68, 1H, dd, J 11.6, 3.6 Hz; 4.41, 1H, dd, J 11.6, 5.2 Hz) was assigned to methine and methylene hydrogens of C-25 and C-27 respectively. The structure of withafastuosin B was thus deduced as 32. Chemical evidence in support of the structure came from the conversion of withafastuosin B to withametelin F (37) by treatment with Ac₂O-pyridine at 60° for 16 h²⁷.

Datumelin (41), isolated from *D. metel*⁹, is no doubt a C₂₈-steroid built on ergostane framework but it cannot be regarded as a withanolide as it lacks the lactone ring in the side-chain. Its structural resemblance with withametelin (35)

is quite manifest and its formation from withametelin by methanolysis with a rather unusual alkyl-oxygen cleavage may be visualised. Alternatively, it may be regarded as one derived from the immediate precursor of withametelin which

Daturalactone-1 (2) : R=OH, R₁=H
(source : *D.q*^{2,22}, *D.fx*, *D.str*, *D.h*⁴)

Daturalactone-2 (3) : R+R₁=O
(*D.q*^{19,22})

Daturalactone-4 (4) : R=R₁=H
(*D.q*²⁴)

Daturalactone-3 (5) : R=R₂=H, R₁=OH
(source : *D.q*²³, *D.fx*, *D.h*⁴)

Lycium substance B (6) : R=R₁=R₂=H
(*D.fx*, *D.h*, *D.q*⁴, *D.m*¹⁶)

Nicandrin B (7) : R=OH, R₁=R₂=H
(=Withaferoxolide) (*D.fx*, *D.q*, *D.h*^{4,26})

Withametelin E (8) : R=H, R₁=R₂=OH
(*D.m*¹⁶)

Withanicandrin (9) : R+R₁=O, R₂=H
(*D.fx*, *D.q*, *D.h*^{4,20})

Withastramonolide (10) : R=R₂=OH, R₁=H
(*D.str*³, *D.h*⁴)

12-Deoxywithastramonolide (11) : R=R₁=H, R₂=OH
(*D.m*¹⁵)

Daturametelin A (12) : R=H, R₁=OGlc, Δ^{2,5}
(Source : *D.m*⁵)

Daturametelin B (13) : R=OH, R₁=OGlc, Δ^{2,5}
(*D.m*⁵)

Daturametelin E (14) : R=OH, R₁=OMe, 3β-OSO₃H, Δ⁵
(*D.m*⁶)

Daturaturin A (15) : R=H, R₁=OGlc, 7α-OH, Δ^{2,5}
(*D.tr*²⁵)

Secowithametelin (16) : R=OH, R₁=OMe, Δ^{2,5}
(Daturametelin C) (*D.m*^{6,14})

Withametelin C (17) : R=OH, R₁=H, 5α-OH, 6β-OH
(*D.m*¹⁶)

Withametelin D (18) : R=OH, R₁=H, 5α-OH, 6β-OH, Δ²
(*D.m*¹⁶)

Withafastuosin D (19) : R=R₁=OH, 5β,6β-epoxy, Δ²
(*D.fst*²⁸)

Withafastuosin E (20) : R=R₁=OH, 5α-OH, 6β-OH, Δ²
(*D.fst*²⁸)

Withafastuosin F (21) : R=R₁=OH, 5α-OH, 6β-OH, 12β-OH, Δ²
(*D.fst*²⁹)

Withametelin H (22) : R=OH, R₁=OMe, 5α-OH, 6β-OH, Δ²
(*D.m*¹⁸)

Withatatuln (23) : R=OH, R₁=H, 5β, 6β-epoxy
(*D.il*³⁰)

Withatatuln B (24) : R=OH, R₁=H, 5β,6β-epoxy, 12β-OH, Δ²
(*D.il*³¹)

Withatatuln C (25) : R=OH, R₁=H, 6β-OH, 12β-OH, Δ^{2,4}
(*D.il*³¹)

Withatatuln D (26) : R=OH, R₁=H, 5α-OH, 6β-OH, 12β-OH, Δ²
(*D.il*³¹)

Withatatuln E (27) : R=OH, R₁=H, 5β,6β-epoxy, Δ²
(*D.il*³²)

Daturametelin D (28) : R=OMe, Δ^{2,5}
(=Datumetelin) (Source : *D.m*^{6,7,11})

Daturametelin G (29) : R=OGlc, Δ^{2,5}
(*D.m*⁶)

Daturilnol (30) : R=OH, Δ^{2,5}
(*D.m*¹⁰)

Withafastuosin A (31) : R=OH, 5β,6β-epoxy
(*D.fst*²⁷)

Withafastuosin B (32) : R=OH, 5β,6β-epoxy, Δ²
(*D.fst*²⁷)

- Daturametelin F (33) : 3β -OSO₃H, Δ^5
(Source : *D.m*⁶)
- Isowithametelin (34) : $\Delta^{3,5}$
(*D.m*¹³)
- Withametelin (35) : $\Delta^{2,5}$
(=Daturilin)
(*D.m*^{8,12,13})
- Withametelin B (36) : 6β -OH, $\Delta^{2,4}$
(*D.m*¹⁵)
- Withametelin F (37) : $5\beta,6\beta$ -epoxy, Δ^2
(*D.m*¹⁷)
- Withametelin G (38) : 5α -OH, 6β -OH, Δ^2
(*D.m*¹⁷)
- Withafastuosin C (39) : 3β -OMe, $5\beta,6\beta$ -epoxy
(*D.fst*¹⁸)

Daturaturin B (40)
(Source : *D.tr*²⁵)

Datumelin (41)
(Source : *D.m*⁹)

Explanation of abbreviation of various *Datura* species are :

D.fx=*D.ferox*; *D.fst*=*D.fastuosa*; *D.h*=*D.hybrids*; *D.m*=*D.metel*;
D.q=*D.quercifolia*; *D.str*=*D.stramonium* (var. *D.tatula* for 2,
and var. *D.violaceae* for 10); *D.tl*=*D.tatula*; *D.tr*=*D.tatura*.

could not lactonise because of prior methylation of the hydroxyl group at C-22.

An inspection of the structures of withanolides of *D. fastuosa* and *D. tatula* reveals some interesting features. While the withanolides of *D. fastuosa* are oxygenated at C-21 and C-27, those of *D. tatula* leaves are only oxygenated at C-21, the flower withanolides being additionally oxygenated at C-12 position. Though the withanolide glycosides, daturaturins A and B (40 and 15), isolated from *D. tatura* by the Japanese workers²⁵ are altogether different from the compounds isolated by us from *D. tatula*, the author wonders whether these are two different or the same species.

The occurrence of different chemotypes of the withanolide-bearing plant, *Withania somnifera* is well-documented^{1,36} and it would be interesting to study whether such chemotypes do exist in different *Datura* species.

Withanolides and their relatives are well-known for their diverse biological activities¹ but very little work has been done to assess the bioactivities of *Datura* withanolides. Daturalactone-1 (2) has been reported to be an effective antifertility agent and it showed 73.3% antiimplantation effect³⁷. The estrogenic activity of this compound was also confirmed³⁸. Withafastuosin D (19) exhibited anxiolytic activity and it significantly inhibited immobilisation stress-induced depletion of adrenal corticosterone compared to the control group suggesting anti-stress activity of the compound³⁹. A derivative of withafastuosin D, tested against a panel of tumor cells *in vitro*, showed selectivity for the leukemia cells and 50% growth inhibition was observed at about 10⁻⁸ molar concentration (Courtesy, N.C.I., Bethesda, U.S.A.). Withafastuosin E (20) failed to show antistress and antitumor activity but it significantly reduced the incidence of ulcer and ulcer-index in rats. The results of experiments indicated that the antiulcer effect of withafastuosin E is due to its ability to decrease the offensive acid-pepsin factors of gastric ulcer and enhance the production of prostaglandins^{40,41}.

There is an undiminishing interest in studying the various aspects of this group of compounds and it is expected to intensify with better realisation of their utility.

Acknowledgement

The author's sincere thanks are due to his students, Drs. M. Sahai, Anjana Bagchi, Subhash Sinha, Sujata Kundu, Mohini Gupta, Md. Ali Farboodniay Jahromi, M. Manickam and Anjam Srivastava for their contribution on *Datura* withanolides.

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